

THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE INTEGRATION OF THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

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Abstract. *The article covers the theoretical foundations and issues of integration of interdisciplinary and intra-disciplinary educational process. Also, integration in education is described as a systematic approach to the construction of the content of educational subjects.*

Keywords: *integration, integration, education, educational subjects, didactics, methodology.*

In the period of transition to new educational plans and programs implemented in our country, issues of harmonizing relations between society and the environment, establishing and forming a serious attitude to the environment become important.

The comprehensive development of a person in the process of education is disturbed by the subject content of education. Pedagogues in practice identified the contradiction in the conditions of development of a young person who is studying.

At present, in pedagogical practice, researches on ways of integration of educational process on the basis of interdisciplinarity are continuing. Recognizing the usefulness of the work being carried out, we define its character. Such educational work has a great effect.

The issue of the integration of content and educational goals can be resolved only on the basis of educational philosophy. At the beginning of the philosophy of education based on the methodological apparatus, the ideal norms of science, universal categories should stand.

Their proposal for integration in science education is external integration, but in fact, it is necessary to conduct the integration of sciences on the basis of a deep methodology.

In the content of the newly developing science, there is a possibility of a combination of ideas and methods that appeared in different philosophical currents. Not only natural adaptation, but also continental adaptation is mastered by the philosophy of education.

A number of works are devoted to inter-discipline and intra-discipline relations in education. These problems are the zone of close development of the transition to the integration of academic subjects.

Some aspects of the integrated education, interdisciplinary relations are studied by famous pedagogues (Ya. Komensky, D. Locke, I. Herbert, M. Pestalotti, K. Ushinsky and others), didactics (I.D. Zverev, M.A. Danilov, V.N. Maksimova, S.P. Baranova, N.M. Katkina and others) psychological scientists (E.N. Kabanova, Meller, N.F. Talyzina, Yu.A. Samarina, G.I. Vergeles), medical scientists (M.R. Lvov, V.G. Goretsky, N.N. Svetlovskaya, Yu.M. Kolyagin, G.N. Pristupova).

The word "integration" comes from the Latin integration-restoration, filling, whole word "integer".

According to the modern didactics and methods, the success of education, development and upbringing of students is formed by their understanding of the unity of the world. Integration in education is considered through a systematic approach to the construction of the content of educational subjects.

In this, students' analysis and generalization activities are created. Concepts within the system provide students with knowledge of a whole system of disciplines. (physical, chemical, biological, system of knowledge) wide use of knowledge is observed within the scope of the studied science. Represents the imagination, time, environment, and numerical connections within the system. Intersubjective imagination is the highest level of mental activity.

They combine different systems of knowledge, give an opportunity to know the essence of a phenomenon or process. Based on this knowledge, general concepts emerge. The formation of intersystem views allows them to use knowledge, to subordinate them to each other, to identify gaps in the boundaries of knowledge.

Integration among educational subjects does not negate the system of subjects. Such an approach aimed at deepening the connections and connections between subjects as a way to improve the integration system and eliminate its shortcomings relies on understanding the relationship between differentiation and integration.

The goal of pedagogy is to help teachers in the implementation of integration aimed at uniting elements and parts of different subjects with the same purpose into a whole.

Integration is a source of discovery of new evidence that confirms or deepens the observations and conclusions of teachers in different subjects.

They prevent students from getting tired and nervous by alternating different forms of activity.

Acquaintance with foreign experience shows that integrated sciences, which are the basis for the development of knowledge about nature and society, are included in the curricula of many countries.

Currently, several methods of integration are used. The first is to combine several disciplines into one.

The methods of implementation of the integration can be good or bad, the essence of the problem is to turn away from one of the methods and introduce the integration measures that take into account the age characteristics of teachers at all levels (psychological and physiological).

Currently, it is necessary to develop and test an integrated system of lessons, where the psychological and methodological basis is the establishment of connections between common concepts for a number of educational subjects. At the same time, interdisciplinary relations should be taught at the level of the curriculum and provided with the necessary teaching tools.

What is the essence of educational integration? The concept of "Integration" related to education has 2 meanings:

1. To create a good idea of the surrounding world in the student (where integration is seen as an educational goal).
2. A common platform for the convergence of subject knowledge find (where integration is a learning tool)

Integration is a means of accepting new ideas within the boundaries of subject knowledge. First of all, it is necessary to fill the unknown places among the classified knowledge, to establish connections between them.

It is aimed at increasing the knowledge of the learner, updating the narrow specialization in education. At the same time, it is not necessary to take the place of classical educational prerequisites of integration education, it should only combine the acquired knowledge into a single system. The difficult part of the problem is the dynamic development of integration from the

beginning to the end of education. If at the beginning it was necessary to "know a little about everything", then it is necessary to integrate scattered knowledge and skills, and by the end it is necessary to "know everything about a little", that is, this is specialization at a new level of integration.

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